

DIALOGUE BETWEEN ART AND ARCHITECTURE, PAUL KLEE AND CARLO SCARPA

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SUMMARY

This work stems from an interest in exploring the works of the architect Carlo Scarpa and how contemporary art may have influenced his architecture. It mainly focuses on Scarpa's installations for the Venice Biennale, after World War II, when contemporary art found new spaces of dissemination.

Carlo Scarpa collaborated for more than 20 years with the Venice Biennale, but it was only in 1948, at the first post-war Biennale, that he made his first experience in the field of painting exhibition. He was nominated to design the exhibitions of a few Italian contemporary artists, a retrospective of Paul Klee and works from the Peggy Guggenheim Col-

lection.¹ Particularly successful was the retrospective of Paul Klee, where Carlo Scarpa designed a small room to show Klee's works with an innovative layout. The Klee retrospective represents a fully successful example of how the architect values the artwork. Scarpa demonstrates a great ability to interpret modern art in its essence: with his artistic and cultural training he shows sensitivity in making the senses relate with emotions, perceptions with human intimacy and, ultimately, the viewer with the artwork. The encounter between Scarpa and Klee's works was a long-lasting source of inspiration for the architect.

The Venice Biennale is one of the most important Italian cultural events, having international resonance and participation. In 1948, after 6 years of inactivity, the Venice Biennale XXIV reopened with contemporary art, from Impressionism to the latest avant-gardes, filling the expressive void that Italian culture had suffered during the pre-war fascist period.

Paul Klee was selected to represent Switzerland and Cubist art. Carlo Scarpa, an international well known Venetian architect and designer, was asked to design the spaces in the central pavilion (Italian Pavilion), for the following exhibitions (Room 3, 4, and 5): *Tre pittori italiani tra il 1910 e il 1920* (Carrà, De Chirico, and Morandi), solo shows for Arturo Martini,

Massimo Campigli and Filippo De Pisis and the retrospective of Paul Klee (Room 37). He was also commissioned to design the exhibition of the Peggy Guggenheim Collection, hosted in the Greek Pavilion. His Venetian origin and experience (at the glassmaker factory Venini) made him a natural choice.

Carlo Scarpa was born in 1906 in Venice. He finished his studies at the Royal Institute of Fine Arts, obtaining a diploma in architectural drawing in 1926. At the school he mainly developed his skills in the art of drawing and the use of the different graphic and pictorial techniques, fields in which Scarpa showed an evident propensity. After graduating, he began teaching at the higher institute of architecture in Venice. In parallel, he

acted as an artistic consultant for Murano's glassmaker studios where influences of Braque, Picasso, Léger, and Matisse were recognized in his drawings and paintings.

Designing rooms for the XXIV. Venice Biennale represents Scarpa's first approach to a fine art exhibition and more particularly to a contemporary art exhibition. The final selection of Klee's artworks, made by Rolf Bürgi, one of the founders of the Paul Klee Society, was comprised of 18 pieces: six paintings and twelve watercolors. The choice of these works was difficult both due to the tiny size of the room, and because Klee's most popular pieces had already been exhibited in larger exhibitions around Europe. The pictures included some iconic pieces of the artist, spanning his career from 1919 (*Triple Time*, 1919, 68) to 1940 (*Superior Guard*, 1940, 256). Among the eighteen works on display, three dealt with the theme of the city: *Picture of a Town (Red-Green Gradated) [with the Red Dome]* of 1923, *Part of G.* of 1927 and *Town End* of 1926.

Klee's exhibition was housed in room XXXVII of the central pavilion; a very small semicircular room (850 x 430 cm), with two entrances at either end of the straight wall.

Scarpa dedicated the straight wall to the paintings (**FIG. 1, LEFT**), and the many shorter walls forming the hemicycle to the watercolors (**FIG. 1, RIGHT**). All artworks were exhibited on framed white canvases backed by larger frames with black canvases. No artificial lighting was visible in the room: a white linen sheet was suspended from the ceiling to diffuse and filter light in the environment. The innovative arrangement of the works based upon their resonances and graphic contrasts rather than chronological order, as used at the time, allowed Scarpa to give more prominence to the figurative message of the paintings rather than to the

pictorial evolution of Klee's thought. By means of this presentation, the visitor was invited into a more intimate dialogue with the individual works and with their author's vision.

The arrangement of the panels dedicated to the watercolors followed a broken line (**FIG. 2**), creating a completely new spatiality and accentuating the semicircular shape of the room, almost forming an apse-like space. The path created by these panels begins with a much dilated curve from the entrance on the left and ends approximately in the middle of the room, at one of the four wooden uprights present in the room. A panel oriented almost 90 degrees with respect to the wall opposite the entrances, resumes the path, pushing the visitor to the center of the room, and is followed by another curve, much more contracted, formed by panels slightly offset from each other that end at the entrance on the right. The panels hosting the six paintings were hung parallel to the wall between the two entrances. Only the last panel on the right protruded from the wall towards the center of the room as a flag. The orientation of the panels was thought by the architect to invite the viewer into the ideal position to admire the individual works, and moved according to two circular trajectories, in order not to induce visitors to leave the room (**FIG. 3**).

Scarpa's intent was to promote an active relationship between the viewer and the artwork through the unconscious recognition of some objects, which persisted from one picture to another: each element was part of a plot of figurative resonances. The spaces and partitioning he created in the room itself seemed to recall the geometrical figures, planes, and lines so important to Klee. The height of the panels was defined by the larger painting *The Grey Man and the Coast*, 1938, 125 (**FIG. 4**). This painting was framed by four slightly protruding wooden strips.

Fig. 1
Installation view of the Klee room
designed by Carlo Scarpa at Venice
Biennale XXIV, 1948
© Biennale archive

Fig. 2
Carlo Scarpa, Final floor plan and section
of the Klee room at Venice Biennale XXIV,
1948
(From: Beltramini/Forster/Marini 2000,
Fig. 2, p. 106)
© Archivio Carlo Scarpa, Treviso

Fig. 3
Reconstructed view of the interior of Klee
room at Venice Biennale XXIV (1948), 2021
(wall with watercolors)
© Giacomo Ontano

Fig. 4
Paul Klee, *The Grey Man and the Coast*, 1938, 125, colored paste on burlap, reconstructed frame, 105 x 71 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Livia Klee Donation
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, image archive

Fig. 5
Reconstructed view of the interior of Klee room at Venice Biennale XXIV (1948), 2021 (paintings wall on the left and watercolors on the right)
© Giacomo Ontano

Fig. 6
Paul Klee, *Opened*, 1933, 306, watercolor, pen and pencil on primed muslin on plywood, 40.5 x 55 cm, Private Collection Switzerland, on permanent loan, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, image archive

Fig. 7
Paul Klee, *B. e. H. (Upper Egypt)*, 1929, 38, watercolor and pencil on paper on cardboard, 30 x 45.5 cm, Galerie Thomas, Munich
© Galerie Thomas, Munich

The Step, 1932, 319 was the second fulcrum of the composition which, aligned with the upper edge of *The Grey Man and the Coast*, determined the height of the lower border of all the other paintings (FIG. 5).

The Grey Man and the Coast is characterized by a long vertical zigzag line. It appeared to be well balanced both between the paintings to its left, where the forms dematerialized into points, and those to its right, constructed of chromatic planes and broken lines. By placing *The Step* in a raised position, Scarpa aligned the other four paintings on the visitor's line of sight – *Picture of a Town*, 1923, 90; *EMACHT*, 1932, 68; *Glance out of Red*, 1937, 211; and *Opened*, 1933, 306 (FIG. 6).

Another interesting detail, visible in the drawing of the architect², was the vertical wooden upright that concluded the composition on the right side, opposite to *EMACHT*. The upright was finely drawn and then decorated with various types of

wood. It is easy to trace the weaving of the wood to *B. e. H. (Upper Egypt)*, 1929, 38 (FIG. 7), a watercolor inspired by a journey of Klee to Egypt, where the artist developed the cardinal progression.

The twelve watercolors by Klee were positioned in nine panels, centered with respect to an axis placed 143 cm from the lower edge of the vertical panels, denoting a top-down reading proposal. The choice to arrange the paintings according to a central axis, positioned at a height comparable to the viewer's eyes could have been derived from Le Corbusier, who wrote in the *Le Modulor* (1948): "The human eye is not the eye of a fly, placed within the heart of a polyhedron: it is situated upon the body of man, in twin position on either side of the nose, at an average height of 1.60 m. above ground. That is, in every sense, our tool for the appreciation of the architectural sensation."³

The spatial model that, according to many researchers, inspired Scarpa to

Fig. 8
Floor design by Carlo Scarpa at Olivetti
store, Venice
© Giacomo Ontano

Fig. 9
Paul Klee, *EMACHT*, 1932, 68, oil on cotton,
50 x 64 cm, Kunstmuseum Bern, Livia Klee
Donation
© Kunstmuseum Bern

“complicate” the room with the panels was likely *Opened*, 1933, 306. This painting represents plain surfaces and geometrical objects that, for lack of perspective, do not lead to a concrete solution but float and fold like the pages of an open book. These magical elements were materialized by Scarpa with the wooden panels that work as the frames for Klee’s paintings.

The XXIV. Biennale was the first time Scarpa creatively interacted with Klee’s art. The encounter between Scarpa and the contemporary art of Klee, and with other artists close to Klee, was a long-lasting source of inspiration for the architect. Scarpa was immediately fascinated by the dimensions without place or time, where colors dictated rhythm and geometry. In many architectural examples of Scarpa it was remarkable how the architect thoroughly understood the charisma and the strength of the signs that populate Klee’s paintings. The restoration of the Olivetti shop in Piazza San Marco in Venice in 1957/58 stands as one example (FIG. 8). The arrangement of the tiles on the Venetian floor resembled one of Klee’s paintings (*EMACHT*) (FIG. 9) exhibited at the Biennale. The small tiles in light pastel colors recall similar mosaic motifs in Klee’s painting.

With this intervention Scarpa demonstrated how deeply he assimilated Klee’s work. Scarpa translated his ideas inspired by Klee’s works onto the architectural canvas. They survived the change of scale, keeping the Swiss artist’s figurative strength intact. From the paintings, Scarpa took the “brushstroke” element, repeated quickly and regularly throughout the canvas, transposing it as a floor tile. The objects imported by Scarpa from art or architecture, were elements that could be combined by virtue of their formal eloquence, even if they were changed in scale.

If a brushstroke were transformed into a mosaic tile, could each line, in the same way, correspond to a division of architectural space? It is impossible to dismiss the hypothesis that Scarpa conducted intrinsic research on the figurative structure of the canvas to transpose it into the interior design of the shop. Similar procedures were applied to two other extensions of the Venice Biennale: The Book Pavilion (1950) and the entrance to the Gardens and new Ticket Office (1952).

The Book Pavilion (FIG. 10) was built in 1950. Scarpa was commissioned to build a small oasis of rest and reading in the gardens of the Biennale. He designed a modest-sized pavilion, divided into two parts, one in concrete that housed the book shop and a shallow pool, and one in wood where the exhibitions took place. Although Frank Lloyd Wright’s architecture remained an important reference for Scarpa, the inspiration of his creative

Fig. 10
Book Pavilion, designed by Carlo Scarpa,
1950
© Archivio della Galleria del Cavallino,
Venice

Fig. 11
Paul Klee, *Open Book*, 1930, 206, watercolor
on primed canvas, 45.7 x 42.5 cm, Solomon
R. Guggenheim Museum, Estate of Karl
Nierendorf, By Purchase
© Solomon R. Guggenheim Museum

Fig. 12
Paul Klee, *Picture Book*, 1937, 140, oil and
scratched drawing on primed cardboard,
36.6 x 29.5 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern,
Livia Klee Donation
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, image archive

Fig. 13
Carlo Scarpa, Design drawing for the Book
Pavilion, 1950
© Archivio della Galleria del Cavallino,
Venice

Fig. 14
Wassily Kandinsky, *Green Split*, 1925, oil
on cardboard, 68.7 x 49 cm, Moderna Museet,
Stockholm
© Moderna Museet, Stockholm

process seemed to lie elsewhere. Scarpa declared: "I will make a book for books." This statement offers an unequivocal key to understand his design. A book consists of two elements of equal geometry: the first, rigid and single (the cover), the second, multiple and flexible (pages, a set of equal planes). Its shape is not stable because, when the reader flips through the pages, it changes continuously. These concepts appear in two works of Klee, *Opened* and *Open Book*, 1930, 206 (FIG. 11). In *Opened*, the Swiss-German artist depicts plain surfaces and objects that float and fold like the pages of an open book. In *Open Book*, Klee shows the architecture of a book that gradually unfolds in space, according to time and rhythm characteristic of the painting. Klee's painting seems to illustrate in two dimensions what Scarpa developed in terms of architectural composition.

The structure embodied the idea of a building that changed with time. Like a book, the pavilion was made up of two parts, one variable out of wood, and the other fixed, of concrete, oriented towards the central building. This latter element is composed of planes of different consistency that, on one side, lead to the bookshop entrance and, on the other side, form a sort of backstage area for the pool and a sculpture, changed at every Biennale. This part recalls another of Klee's paintings *Picture Book*, 1937, 140 (FIG. 12) with the book as the protagonist. In this work, planes have a real architectural consistency and the book's page acts as a backstage for the image.

In his own research, Scarpa did not limit himself to the abstract art of the Swiss-German master but references to Theo van Doesburg, Piet Mondrian, and Wassily Kandinsky can also be found. The reference to Kandinsky is easily understood if the Book Pavilion plan (FIG. 13) is considered: there is a remarkable resem-

blance to the structure of his *Green Split* canvas from 1925 (FIG. 14).

Another project that recalls Klee and Kandinsky was the Ticket Office to the Biennale Gardens (1952) (FIG. 15). Scarpa defined it as a circular cabin, consisting of a concrete base and a stained glass window that occupied an angle of about 120° on the base. A large roof was suspended over the cabin, in the shape of a leaf or almond. It consisted of crossbows of wood fixed to a metal frame, supported by a structure of pillars, like the supports of Klee's retrospective of 1948 where the inlays were inspired by Klee's works. The layout of the project seemed to be inspired by the canvas *Connecting Green*, 1926 by Kandinsky (FIG. 16).

To conclude, with Klee's retrospective, Scarpa's thoughts on how to translate inspiration from modern artworks into his architectural designs seemed to be fully manifested. The arrangement of the works, not in chronological order, as per tradition, but by an innovative repetition of colors or graphic signs, evoking both assonance and dissonance of the resulting forms demonstrates the research and the interpretative effort of the works by the architect. The study of the arrangement of the works in the environment, the adaptation of the original volumes to the needs of the exhibition, the prefiguration of the paths, distances, pauses, and lights are the tools used by the architect to bring the visitor closer to the work of art, engaging him in a better visual experience.

The characteristic that Scarpa drew from Klee was an awareness of the importance and the aesthetic, but also emotional value that a certain mark traced on a surface, or a certain relationship between lines, planes, and colors, possessed. Scarpa was immediately fascinated by the dimensions without place or time, where color dictates rhythm and geometry, responding with an abstract interpretation in architectural space.

Fig. 15
 "Biglietteria ai Giardini" [Ticket Office to the Biennale Gardens] by Carlo Scarpa, Venice Biennale, 1952
 (From: Lanzarini 2004, Fig. 72, p. 130)
 © Centro Internazionale di Studi di Architettura Andrea Palladio, Venice

Fig. 16
 Wassily Kandinsky, *Connecting Green*, 1926, oil on canvas, 84 x 57.5 cm, Yoshino Gypsum Collection
 © Yoshino Gypsum Collection

- 1 Ponti 1948.
- 2 Beltramini/Forster/Marini 2000, p.105.
- 3 Le Corbusier 1980, part 1, p. 73.

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